

Synthesis and spectral studies of Schiff base complexes of cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) with 1-methyl-2,6-diethyl piperidone thiosemicarbazone

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Abstract : Schiff base complexes of the type $[M(MDET)_2X_2]$, where M = cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II), MDET = 1-methyl-2,6-diethyl piperidone thiosemicarbazone and X = Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- and ClO_4^- have been prepared. The ligand and metal complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses, magnetic susceptibility, infrared spectra, electronic spectra and molecular conductivity measurements. IR spectral data reveals the compound MDET behaves as neutral bidentate ligand and coordination proposed through azomethine nitrogen and thione sulphur of thiosemicarbazone moiety. The remaining positions of metal ions are satisfied by negative ions, such as Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- and ClO_4^- . The electronic spectral data and magnetic susceptibility values proposed octahedral geometry for the complexes. The molar conductivity were recorded in DMF (10^{-3}) solution and found to be in the range of $3.01-4.6 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$, proposed that all the complexes are non electrolytic in nature.

Keywords : Schiff base, Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , coordination compounds.

Introduction

Schiff base complexes have been receiving considerable attentions¹⁻⁸ on account of their stereochemical significance as well as agricultural and industrial applications. They continue to attract many researchers because of their wide applications in the field of pesticide and in medicine with their highly effective antibacterial and anticoagulant^{9,10} activities. They also useful as antitumour¹¹, anticarcinogenic¹² and plant growth regulators. Keeping the above facts in mind and in continuation of our earlier publications¹³⁻²¹ on Schiff base complexes, we herein report the synthesis and characterization of complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} ions with 1-methyl-2,6-diethyl piperidone thiosemicarbazone (MDET).

Experimental

All the reagents herein used were of analytical grade. The metal contents of all the complexes were estimated using Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer²¹. The IR spectra of ligand and their metal complexes (Table 2) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer using KBr disc. Magnetic susceptibility were measured on Gouy balance using $Hg[Co(NCS)_4]$ as a calibrant.

Electronic spectra were recorded on Cary-2390 spectrophotometer. Molar conductance were recorded on Systronics conductivity-meter model-303 using DMF as a solvent.

Synthesis of the ligand :

Ethanol solution of 1-methyl-2,6-diethyl piperidone (0.01 M) was treated with thiosemicarbazide hydrochloride (0.01 M) dissolved in minimum amount of sodium acetate in tetrahydrofuran. The resulting mixtures were heated on a water bath for 3-4 h with occasional stirring. After cooling, the precipitate was filtered and washed with aqueous ethanol, dried and recrystallised with DMF, m.p. $163 \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ C$; yield 70-75%.

Preparation of the complexes :

The complexes were prepared by mixing the appropriate molar quantities of the ligand and the metal salts using the following procedures. The complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} were prepared by reacting an ethanolic solution of corresponding metal halide/metal nitrate/metal perchlorate with ethanolic solution of the ligand 1-methyl-2,6-diethyl piperidone thiosemicarbazone (MDET) in the molar ratio 1 : 2. The procedure carried out in

each case were of similar nature with a slight variation of timing of reflux. The coloured complexes obtained in each case were cooled, filtered and washed with ethanol several times to remove any excess of the ligand. Finally, the complexes were washed with anhydrous diethyl ether and dried in oven. Yield 70–75%.

Results and discussion

All the complexes were air stable. The analytical data and physical properties of the complexes are summarised in Table 1. The analytical data correspond well with the

general formula $[M(MDET)_2X_2]$, where MDET = 1-methyl-2,6-diethyl piperidone thiosemicarbazone; $X = Cl^-$, Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- and ClO_4^- . The low value of molar conductance of the complexes also supported the proposed structure of the complexes.

Infrared spectra :

IR spectrum of the ligand MDET exhibits a strong and medium band at 1480 cm^{-1} assignable²²⁻²⁴ to $\nu_{C=N}$. In the spectra of the complexes this band shows red shift with slightly reduced intensity. The shift of the band and change in intensity proposes coordination of the azomethine

Table 1 Analytical, colour, mol. wt., magnetic susceptibility, electronic spectra, molar conductivity and decomposition temperature of the ligand MDET and their metal complexes

Compd. (Colour)	Mol. mass	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				μ_{eff} (B.M.)	λ_{max} electronic (cm^{-1})	Ω_m (Ω^{-1} $\text{cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	DT ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
		M	C	N	H				
MDET (Colourless)	240	–	54.67 (54.54)	23.21 (23.33)	8.21 (8.33)	–	–	–	163
$[\text{Co}(\text{MDET})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ (Yellowish red)	609.93	9.61 (9.66)	43.11 (43.28)	18.22 (18.30)	6.49 (6.55)	4.96	13200, 19200	3.03	217
$[\text{Co}(\text{MDET})_2\text{Br}_2]$ (Yellowish red)	698.748	8.50 (8.43)	37.62 (37.78)	16.11 (16.02)	5.56 (5.72)	4.94	13400, 19600	3.02	201
$[\text{Co}(\text{MDET})_2\text{I}_2]$ (Red)	792.73	7.38 (7.43)	33.21 (33.30)	14.26 (14.12)	5.00 (5.04)	5.24	13500, 19800	3.01	212
$[\text{Co}(\text{MDET})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ (Deep red)	662.93	8.96 (8.88)	39.99 (39.82)	16.98 (16.89)	5.92 (6.03)	5.21	13700, 20000	3.5	236
$[\text{Co}(\text{MDET})_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2]$ (Light green)	737.03	8.09 (7.98)	35.88 (35.77)	15.25 (15.17)	5.33 (5.42)	5.10	12900, 19100	3.7	238
$[\text{Ni}(\text{MDET})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ (Brown)	605.71	9.78 (9.69)	43.68 (43.58)	18.62 (18.49)	6.71 (6.60)	3.16	10000, 15600, 24000	4.1	308
$[\text{Ni}(\text{MDET})_2\text{Br}_2]$ (Deep brown)	698.528	8.31 (8.40)	37.88 (37.79)	15.94 (16.03)	5.86 (5.72)	3.11	10500, 15800, 23800	4.6	238
$[\text{Ni}(\text{MDET})_2\text{I}_2]$ (Brownish red)	792.51	7.34 (7.40)	33.42 (33.31)	14.21 (14.13)	5.12 (5.04)	3.05	10700, 16000, 24200	4.5	240
$[\text{Ni}(\text{MDET})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ (Deep red)	662.71	8.94 (8.85)	40.01 (39.83)	17.02 (16.90)	5.94 (6.03)	3.03	11000, 15400, 23500	4.4	243
$[\text{Ni}(\text{MDET})_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2]$ (Red)	737.71	8.04 (7.95)	35.81 (35.76)	15.23 (15.18)	5.50 (5.42)	3.01	10900, 16200, 24500	4.3	260
$[\text{Cu}(\text{MDET})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ (Blue)	614.54	10.28 (10.33)	42.84 (42.95)	18.31 (18.22)	6.62 (6.50)	1.89	11400, 15000	3.8	250
$[\text{Cu}(\text{MDET})_2\text{Br}_2]$ (Blue)	703.258	8.96 (9.03)	37.41 (37.53)	16.04 (15.92)	5.73 (5.68)	1.86	11600, 15200	3.6	251
$[\text{Cu}(\text{MDET})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ (Blue)	677.54	9.42 (9.37)	39.08 (38.96)	16.66 (16.53)	6.04 (5.96)	1.84	11700, 15300	3.4	255
$[\text{Cu}(\text{MDET})_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2]$ (Deep red)	792.54	8.63 (8.55)	35.46 (35.55)	14.93 (15.08)	5.21 (5.38)	1.91	11900, 15500	3.7	273

DT = Decomposition Temperature.

Table 2. Salient features of IR spectral data (cm^{-1}) for ligand MDET and its metal complexes

Comps.	$\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$	$\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}}$	$\nu_{\text{M}-\text{N}}$	$\nu_{\text{M}-\text{S}}$	$\nu_{\text{M}-\text{X}}$	$\nu_{\text{M}-\text{O}}$
MDET	1480 s,m	800 s,b				
[Co(MDET) ₂ Cl ₂]	1450 m,b	755 m,b	410 m	470 m	255 m	
[Co(MDET) ₂ Br ₂]	1455 m,b	760 m,b	415 m	470 m	265 m	
[Co(MDET) ₂ I ₂]	1455 m,b	755 m,b	420 m	465 m	270 m	
[Co(MDET) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	1450 m,b	760 m,b	415 m	460 m		520 m
[Co(MDET) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂]	1455 m,b	755 m,b	420 m	450 m		535 m
[Ni(MDET) ₂ Cl ₂]	1450 m,b	760 m,b	425 m	455 m	295 m	
[Ni(MDET) ₂ Br ₂]	1455 m,b	755 m,b	430 m	460 m	305 m	
[Ni(MDET) ₂ I ₂]	1455 m,b	760 m,b	410 m	455 m	315 m	
[Ni(MDET) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	1450 m,b	760 m,b	410 m	450 m		530 m
[Ni(MDET) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂]	1455 m,b	760 m,b	420 m	460 m		525 m
[Cu(MDET) ₂ Cl ₂]	1455 m,b	755 m,b	425 m	465 m	285 m	
[Cu(MDET) ₂ Br ₂]	1450 m,b	750 m,b	430 m	470 m	290 m	
[Cu(MDET) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	1450 m,b	755 m,b	415 m	470 m		510 m
[Cu(MDET) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂]	1455 m,b	710 m,b		470 m		530 m

m = medium, s = strong, b = broad.

N with metal ion. The infrared spectrum of the ligand shows a strong and broad band at 800 cm^{-1} assigned^{22,23-25} to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}}$. In the spectra of the complexes this band also shows red shift indicating coordination takes place through thione S atom of thiosemicarbazone moiety.

The conclusive evidence of bonding of ligand to metal ion through oxygen atom of either nitrate or perchlorate ion, N atom of azomethine group and thione S of thiosemicarbazone moiety is supported by the appearance of bands due to $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{O}}$ ^{22,23,26} at $535\text{--}510 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{S}}$ ^{22,23-26} at $470\text{--}450 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{N}}$ ^{22,23,26} at $430\text{--}420 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. The evidence of metal-halogen linkage is supported by the low molar conductance values²⁷ of the complexes in the range $3.1\text{--}4.6 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and appearance of a band in the region $315\text{--}255 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which assigned^{22,23,26} to $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{X}}$.

Nitrate complexes show characteristic medium intensity bands at 1300 and 1140 cm^{-1} with a separation of 160 cm^{-1} due to monodentate linkage of nitrate group. Combination bands at 1660 and 1640 cm^{-1} with a separation of 20 cm^{-1} confirming the monodentate behaviour of the nitrate²⁸ group. The monodentate behaviour of perchlorate complexes were confirmed due to the presence of four infrared bands at 1130 , 1050 , 650 and 620 cm^{-1} suggesting monodentate behaviour of perchlorate group²⁹.

On the basis of above discussion on IR spectral data,

it is proposed that the ligand MDET, acts in a neutral bidentate manner. The remaining coordination positions of metal ions are satisfied by negative ions, such as Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- and ClO_4^- .

Electronic spectra and magnetic susceptibility of the complexes :

The cobalt(II) complexes exhibit two bands in the regions at $13700\text{--}12900 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $20000\text{--}19100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which are assigned to the transitions, ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(P) \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ respectively, suggesting octahedral³⁰ geometry for the complexes. The proposed geometry are further supported^{31,32} by the high magnetic moment value in the range, $4.94\text{--}5.24 \text{ B.M.}$ The nickel(II) complexes display three spectral bands in the regions $11000\text{--}10000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $16200\text{--}15400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $24500\text{--}23500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributing to transitions, ${}^3T_{2g}(F) \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^3T_{1g}(P) \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}(F)$ respectively, suggesting octahedral³⁰ geometry for Ni^{II} complexes. The proposed geometry of Ni^{II} complexes is further supported^{31,32} by the magnetic moment value in the range $3.01\text{--}3.16 \text{ B.M.}$ The copper(II) complexes exhibit two spectral bands in the regions, $11900\text{--}11200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $15500\text{--}14500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which are assigned to the transitions, ${}^2T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^2E_g$ and charge transfer band which suggest octahedral³⁰ geometry for the copper(II) complexes. The magnetic moment value of copper(II) complexes lies in the range $1.84\text{--}1.91 \text{ B.M.}$

Conclusion :

On the basis of above studies the complexes of cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) are tentatively proposed to possess octahedral geometry as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. $[M(MDET)_2X_2]$, $M = Co^{II}$ and Ni^{II} ; $X = Cl^-$, Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- and ClO_4^- ; $M = Cu^{II}$; $X = Cl^-$, Br^- , NO_3^- and ClO_4^- ; MDET = 1 methyl-2,6-diethyl piperidone thiosemicarbazone.

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